

ECONOMIC INDICATORS, COMMODITY AND PRICE, RESEARCH OF PRODUCT TYPES IN "AGROBRAVO" LLC

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Abstract. *In this article, the processes of using statistical methods in the marketing research of enterprises in the conditions of the market economy, its content, the use of today's research methods, the placement of advertisements in the market and the formation of quality marketing research are considered.*

Keywords: *enterprise, process, market, dairy products, strategy, income, assortment.*

INTRODUCTION. During the years of independence, a national economy based on market relations was established in Uzbekistan. The demand and interest in the knowledge of market relations and the operation of the market economy in the life of society has increased significantly. Life itself has set the agenda to create textbooks and training manuals that incorporate knowledge about the market and are also combined with the experience of developed countries. Marketing research is one of the most successful tools that help organizations excel in the market. Getting the right information about customers' tastes and preferences is the key to business success. Marketing research provides information about consumers and their attitudes towards various products, pricing, distribution and promotion strategies.

The "product-market" matrix is also widely used in the expansion of the company's product assortment program. The "product-market" matrix focuses on the company's entry into new markets and the adoption of new products. This matrix is formed depending on the company's capabilities, products, markets, competitive situation, consumers and direction of activity. The main thing is that the company develops marketing strategies based on its resources and developing sectors.

This matrix envisages strategy development based on market and product updates. The starting point is the difference between the real and planned development of the enterprise. This means that the company's goal cannot be achieved using the previous strategy. A goal is needed, or it needs to be corrected, or a new strategic path must be sought.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. The matrix consists of four fields, situations arising from the influence of two factors determining the position of the enterprise (growth and market and product changes):

- the enterprise operates with existing (old) products in the existing market;
- the enterprise offers a new product to the existing market;
- the enterprise enters a new market with existing (old) products;
- the company enters a new market with new products.

A company's marketing efforts determine the direction of each strategic quadrant. In particular, the market entry strategy, as a rule, promotes goods with traditional buyers, increases

market share, attracts buyers from competitors or new consumers. Based on the matrix, four alternative strategies are used.

Table 1

Production indicators of "AgroBravo" LLC in 2018-2021

No	Indicator name	Amount by years			
		2018	2019	2020	2021
1	Production volume, million soms	7735.7	7983.6	11402.1	12588.5
2	Annual growth rates of production, %	105	117.98	120.15	241.4
3	Change compared to 2018, %	105	117.98	118.93	132.5

According to the data, "AgroBravo" LLC is constantly increasing production volumes. 2021 8.5 billion by the year. Products worth 210.9 million soms were produced, which is 1.2 times more than in 2018. We can clearly observe the change of production volumes in the following diagrams.

Table 2

Analysis of the composition, structure and dynamics of the company's income

Indicators	2021 year		2022 year		Change (+,-)	
	amount, thousand soms	in total, %	amount, thousand soms	in total, %	thousand soms	share
Product net from the sale of (goods, works and services). revenue	12679864	99.46	14281693	90.2	1601829	-0.26
The main activity other income	64791	0.51	1534188	9.7	1469397	+9.19
Financial operating income	3633	0.03	18538	0.1	14905	+0.07
Total revenues	12748288	100.0	15834419	100.0	3086131	-

The conclusions based on the data show that the total sources of income in the enterprise increased by 3086211 thousand soms in 2022 compared to 2021. Despite the fact that the share of net income from the sale of products (goods, work and services) in the total income decreased from 99.46% in 2021 to 90.2% by 2022, the increase in absolute amounts was 1601829 thousand soms. Income from financial activities in the income structure also has a growth indicator, that is, compared to 2021, it increased by 22,905 thousand soms in 2022. In 2021, the share of other incomes of the main activity was 0.51%, while in 2022 this indicator reached 9.7%, and the increase in absolute amounts was 2,269,397 thousand soms.

It is necessary to develop the necessary measures to increase the activity of financial activity of the enterprise.

The results of the analysis of the changes in the composition of the company's income show that the economic entity has the opportunity to further increase its income.

Table 3

Analysis of the dynamics of the use of enterprise income indicators

T/p	Indicators	2021 year	2022 year	Change(+,-)	Rate of change, %
1	Income (D)	12748288	15834419	+3086211	124.2
2	Cost (X)	12685787	15767233	+3082246	124.3
3	Profit (loss) (line 1-line 2)R	62501	67186	+4685	107.5
4	Average annual value of balance sheet assets (A)	21704870	17866915	+4162045	210.3
5	Sales revenue (N)	12679864	22281693	+1601829	112.6
6	Rate of return on balance sheet assets, % (line 3: line 4) (f)	0.456	0.376	-0.08	82.5
7	Rate of return on sales, % (line 3: line.5) (X)	0.493	0.471	-0.022	95.5

The method of analyzing the composition and structure of the company's income and expenses is widely used in practice, and its results are important. In order to further deepen the analysis, it is necessary to evaluate the indicators of effective use of funds (expenses) based on the data of Table 3 through coefficients widely used in financial analysis. The growth rates of income and expenses in the table are close to each other. The growth of the product volume was 112.6 percent, and the income was higher than the expenses. High growth rates of the above-mentioned indicators decreased from 0.456 to 0.376% of return on balance sheet assets, from 0.493% to 0.471% of return on sales.

Table 4

Assortment of products of "AgroBravo" LLC in 2019-2022, million soms

No	Product type	Annual production, million soms				Annual growth, %		
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2019	2020	2021
1	Milk and yogurt	1542.7	4089.4	2159.5	3387.3	265.1	52.8	156.6
2	Butter and margarine	4693.8	3694.5	5570.3	4893.9	78.7	150.8	87.8
3	Condensed and dry milk	18.4	12.3	232.0	486.2	66.9	1888.9	209.6
4	Cheese products and brinza	797.6	391.1	183.1	404.4	49.0	46.8	220.9
5	Ice cream	417.2	11.3	151.8	155.5	2.7	1339.8	102.3
	Total	8745.7	9443.6	10402.1	11688.5	107.98	110.15	111.4

As can be seen from the information presented in the table, there is an increase in production in "AgroBravo" LLC for the main positions of the assortment. We can only see a decrease in the production of cheese products and brinza.

At the same time, it is necessary to analyze the changes in the composition of the assortment in order to draw conclusions about individual assortment positions. We will study the share of product types in the total production.

Table 5

The composition of the assortment of products of "AgroBravo" LLC in 2019-2022,%

No	Product type	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	Milk and yogurt	17.64	43.29	20.76	28.98
2	Butter and margarine	53.67	39.11	53.55	41.87
3	Condensed milk and dry milk	0.21	0.13	2.23	4.16
4	Cheese products and brinza	9,12	4.14	1.76	3.46
5	Ice cream	4.77	0.12	1.46	1.33
6	Others	9,12	4.14	1.76	3.46
	Total	100	100	100	100

Table 6

"AgroBravo" LLC analysis of sales activity

No	Naming	Die. one.	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	Total sales	million amount	41,098.87	45,861.18	52 162.55	48,638.12	88 148.51
	Including:						
2	Total (in currency):	a thousand dollar	18426.22	23141.92	18828.51	24135.47	18628.92
2.1	Export	a thousand dollar	8949.62	7983.24	6947.61	15035.96	8569.32
2.2	Domestic market	a thousand dollar	10774.9	17058.68	12080.9	9099.51	10174.9

SWOT analysis of "AgroBravo" LLC

<p>Strengths of the company: The enterprise has chosen the appropriate market segment; Has its own competitive personnel; When choosing a partner, the partner is chosen taking into account all possibilities; Great attention is also paid to the quality of goods.</p>	<p>Weakness of the company: Less use of all information and communication tools; Less distribution activity in the enterprise. Lack of store network of the enterprise;</p>
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<p>Company capabilities: The enterprise may open its own stores in the course of its activities; Potential for greater consumer engagement.</p>	<p>Risks of the enterprise: Competitive enterprises to the enterprise; the emergence of new technical means; volatility of consumer needs and other risks.</p>
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As mentioned above, the sustainable development of any industry is directly related to the production and sale of goods that are in demand. This, in turn, requires effective organization of marketing activities of network enterprises, regular study of the furniture market, taking into account the wishes of consumers, detailed analysis of purchasing process factors. Technological change, the increasing role of social media, demographic changes and the increasing purchasing power of women are key factors that must be considered in the marketing efforts of furniture manufacturers and retailers. We, the history, culture, tradition,

Conclusions and suggestions

Market research is one of the most effective ways to get information about your customer base, competitors, and the overall market. The purpose of conducting market research is to equip your company with the information it needs to make informed decisions. This is especially important when a small business is trying to determine the viability of a new business idea, wants to move into a new market, or is launching a new product or service.

Market research helps businesses make informed decisions because by using data and insights, companies can develop strategies based on solid facts and evidence rather than guesswork. This will be more effective.

Simply put, market research is the process of using research to increase sales or revenue in the shortest amount of time for maximum profit.

The most important thing in this definition is that marketing research helps business owners or marketing managers to make decisions just like in any research enterprise. Marketing research sheds light on customer preferences, long-term profitability of business operations, and other product-oriented concerns.

In the information age, it pays to be creative and resourceful. The Internet provides a tremendous amount of information that can help you conduct marketing research without leaving your home.

There are many methods available today with tools such as Google Analytics and government websites. You don't even have to leave your home to study the market.

Marketing strategies work best when they are based on a systematic assessment of consumer preferences. What do consumers want? How will they respond to the product or service? Marketing research answers these questions.

Hence, market analysis can be defined as the process of evaluating consumer preferences using a systematic approach like marketing research etc.

In summary, marketing research is a tool that managers and business owners can use to better understand their customers and deliver their goods or services in a way that their customers want. Informed decisions are better than a hit-and-miss approach that doesn't guarantee the desired results.

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